

TEACHER ASSESSMENT OVERVIEW

UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: Teaching is an art. Every single teacher they must have their own way to teach their students. The writer belief that the belief of teacher according good teaching-learning process must be different one to other. Seems like a same method being used by different teacher perhaps the result will not same or perhaps will be really different.

Keywords: Teaching, learning, assessing, students.

ОБЗОР ОЦЕНКИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЯ

ВУЗА

Аннотация: Преподавание – это искусство. У каждого учителя должен быть свой собственный способ учить своих учеников. Отношение хорошего процесса преподавания и обучения должны отличаться друг от друга. Похоже, что один и тот же метод используется другим учителем, возможно, результат будет не таким же или, возможно, будет действительно другим.

Ключевые слова: преподавание, обучение, оценивание, студенты.

بررسی اجمالی ارزشیابی معلمان
دانشگاه

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ازبکستان

چکیده: تدریس یک هنر است. هر معلمی باید روش خاص خود را برای آموزش دانش آموزان داشته باشد. نگرش یک فرآیند خوب آموزش و یادگیری باید با یکدیگر متفاوت باشد. به نظر می رسد که همان روش توسط معلم دیگری استفاده می شود، نتیجه ممکن

است یکسان نباشد یا در واقع متفاوت باشد.

کلیدواژه: آموزش، یادگیری، ارزشیابی، دانش آموزان

Introduction

There are many theories that an English teacher can use as a method or technique to teach students. The way of teaching is very diverse. We cannot claim that our way of teaching is the best, or we cannot claim that any one theory is the best. The whole method or the whole theory and the whole learning process need not be perfect. The theory must have strengths and weaknesses. And we, as educators, must know that we are not perfect and in the process of learning, we must have many weaknesses. Based on this, we, as teachers, must study again and again in order to develop the knowledge and skills that we have. In particular, as an English teacher, we must learn from an expert. This is because teaching English is not easy, so we need advice from an expert so that we can teach our student more accurately and effectively. If we follow the judgments of the experts, the learning process will be better, because the theory found by the expert must be tested, and in order to find the theory, the expert must conduct a detailed study. Thus, in this case, the author believes that, as teachers, we must give our assessment to the learning process that we have done. To make a reflection based on the fact that we know our strengths and weaknesses so that we can make some assessment to improve our technique and skills. In this article, we would like to summarize the teaching assessment from an international journal and hope that this article will be useful to all readers.

1. Shaukat Ali Raza, Syed Abir Hassan Naqvi and Ahmed Sohail Lodi (2011)

The title of their study is *Assessing the Need for Teacher Development at the University of Pakistan: A Student Perspective*. This study examined the opinion of students on the need to improve the qualifications of teachers at a Pakistani university. The first research question was raised to explore the need for advanced training of teachers at the University of Pakistan. The second research question concerned the change in the degree of need for pedagogical development of teachers, perceived by students. The third research question concerned the differences in opinions of respondents regarding their background variables. The sample consisted of 670 students from 67 departments of 33 faculties of 15 state universities. The data were collected using a self-composed questionnaire. Principal component factor analysis identified three factors, namely the art of teaching, the science of teaching, and the sociology of teaching, for which mean scores, alpha coefficients, and correlation were calculated. For analysis of significance and variance, one-sample t-test, independent-sample t-test, and one-way ANOVA were used. The profile of respondents showed that in the gender category there were 385 (57%) men and 285 (43%) women. The spread of disciplines was found to be engineering 41 (06%), social sciences 300 (45%), physical sciences 118 (18%), business 79 (12%), languages 68 (10%) and agriculture 64 (09%). The distribution of respondents by educational programs was established as graduate 108 (16%), Master 507 (76%), M Phil 36 (05%) and PhD 19 (03%). The finding shows that students from most of the sample universities in Pakistan appear to be dissatisfied with the arts, sciences, and sociology of their teachers' teaching. Teaching consists of sociology, art and science. Teacher behavior in and out of the classroom; Teacher feedback patterns and teacher-student relationships are of great importance in student development. The sociology of teaching, the art of teaching, and the science of teaching, respectively, are not considered excellent, and the students of Pakistani universities are not completely satisfied, as they indicated a high degree of need for faculty development in these areas. By comparison, the sociology of teaching was ranked

as the weakest area of university teaching, while the arts and education sciences, respectively, were in a relatively better position.

2. Maria A. Wamsley, MD, Katherine A. Julian and Joyce E. Wipf, MD (2004)

The title of their study is Literature Review of Resident Teacher Curricula. Can training courses make a difference? The purpose of this study is to study methods for evaluating resident training courses and to evaluate the effectiveness of these training courses. The research questions of this study are what methods were used in assessing the recall of memories of the residents' training courses. How is the effectiveness of face-to-face training courses evaluated?

1. Cornella RMG, Fluit, MD, Richard Grof, PhD, and Michelle Wensing, PhD. (2010)

The title of their study is “Assessing the Quality of Clinical Teachers”; A systematic review of the content and quality of clinical teacher assessment questionnaires. The objectives of this study are a systematic review of the content

Amy J. Warner (writer, educator)

The title of her research is Quantitative and Qualitative Evaluations of the Impact of Linguistic Theory on Computer Science. This study explored the relationship between linguistics and computer science. Overall, this study examined both the extent and nature of the contribution of linguistic theory to information science research from 1950 to 1984. In particular, it has attempted to provide both an indication and a measure of the use of cited sources of linguistic theory within a body of research. thematic literature on informatics through both quantitative and qualitative analysis of cited sources. In order to answer the previously raised questions, a citation analysis was performed as follows. First of all, the CITING literature (computer science) was defined as all full-length articles in the part of the computer science serial literature. Second, the CITED (linguistic theory) literature was identified and extracted from the bibliographies and

footnotes of the citing computer science article. Thirty times each reference to linguistic theory was identified as belonging to a particular branch of linguistics. Fourthly, each reference to a linguistic theory was considered in the context of its citation and qualitatively classified. The results of this citation analysis study show that linguistic theory may not have been widely used by computer science researchers. However, while the overall citation frequency was quite low, further analysis of the data revealed citation patterns and practices, suggesting some reasons for the possible underutilization of linguistic theory in computer science research. Then it was suggested that linguistic theory is expanding the scope of its research; that computer scientists may not be aware of this fact; and therefore it is premature to conclude that linguistic theory has only limited application in computer science.

John J. Chiodo (writer, educator, scientist)

The title of this study is Student Perceptions of Teaching. Assessing their mental images of teaching the social sciences. This study attempted to evaluate the ideas and beliefs of students entering a social sciences degree program. Using drawings and written statements, the authors developed an assessment tool that evaluates social science students' beliefs about social science teaching. Fifty-two average social science teachers took part in a study that examined the use of the assessment tool. We see the use of the tool as a way for pre-service students to reflect on their personal beliefs about social science teaching, and to help educators understand how their students' views and beliefs align with their approach to learning. The result of this study showed that the social science teacher assessment analyzed students' drawings and written comments related to their perception of themselves teaching social sciences. The analysis was carried out in three areas: and the learning environment.

Conclusion

Based on the data we have summarized, we conclude that there are many theories related to learning assessment. According to the writer, in different

countries they have different theories. I think it's because students from different countries should be different. And according to the theory that the writer understood, the theory of teaching is always growing every year. So a theory that was popular being studied at this time next year may not be popular again, and it is indeed possible to replace it with a new theory. Therefore, as teachers, we must be more dynamic and always follow the information, because at this time information spreads very quickly. Sophisticated technology has changed society, it has changed students, and as teachers we must develop our skills to teach our students, because today's students are different from the students of the past. And students in the future will also be different. So, as teachers, we must always be learning in order to get better and better.

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